

Electron Spin and Atomic Diamagnetism

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Abstract

This paper demonstrates that electron spin arises from the electron moving forward along a cylindrical helical trajectory. This model can simultaneously explain the Stern–Gerlach experiment and the phenomenon that an electron beam does not split in a magnetic field. The paper further points out that a necessary condition for diamagnetism is the formation of paired electrons within molecules or atoms, and that there are four possible ways for molecules or atoms to form such electron pairs.

Introduction

In 1922, the experiment by O. Stern and W. Gerlach discovered that a beam of silver atoms splits into two beams in a gradient magnetic field [1–3]; this experiment is known as the Stern–Gerlach (S–G) experiment. In 1925, G. E. Uhlenbeck and S. A. Goudsmit proposed the concept of electron spin [4]. Later, Stern and other scientists found that atomic beams of H, Li, Na, K, Cu, and Au also split into two beams, whereas atomic beams of Sn, Pb, Cd, Hg, and others do not split [5–10]. Some people believe that electron spin has two values ($-1/2$ and $+1/2$). This viewpoint is incorrect, because for more than a century no one has been able to split an electron beam into two beams using a magnetic field, and to this day the concrete physical nature of electron spin remains unknown. In the past, atomic diamagnetism was explained as

arising from the precession of electron orbital motion, but no one has stated that the formation of electron pairs is the necessary condition for the emergence of diamagnetism. New findings on these two issues will be presented below.

Theory and Discussion

Electron spin is not rotation about its own central axis; rather, it is the electron moving forward along a cylindrical helical path. Below we prove why an electron can move along a cylindrical helix.

An electron moves with velocity v_{\perp} in the Z-direction, producing a magnetic field B. Here, μ_0 is the vacuum permeability, and θ is the angle between v_{\perp} and r.

$$B = e\mu_0 v_{\perp} \sin\theta / (4\pi r^2) \quad (1)$$

e is the electron charge, and r is the distance from the observation point to the center of the electron.

The electron is not a point particle; it occupies a finite spatial region extending from r_0 to r, where r_0 is the minimum radius.

$$B_0 = e\mu_0 v_{\perp} \sin\theta / (4\pi r_0^2) \quad (2)$$

The average magnetic field is B_1 , and the geometric mean value of the magnetic field is taken as $B_1 = \sqrt{BB_0}$:

$$B_1 = e\mu_0 v_{\perp} \sin\theta / (4\pi r r_0) \quad (3)$$

The magnetic field B_1 causes the electron to experience the Lorentz force, making it undergo circular motion at speed v_{\perp} in a direction perpendicular to the Z-axis. When the Lorentz force balances the centrifugal force generated by the electron's circular

motion, we have:

$$f = e v_{\perp} B_1 = m \frac{v_{\perp}^2}{r} \quad (4)$$

$$v_{\perp} = \frac{erB_1}{m} \quad (5)$$

It is precisely v_{\perp} that gives the electron its cylindrical helix motion. Substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (5) yields:

$$v_{\perp} = \frac{e^2 \mu_0 v_{-} \sin\theta}{4\pi m r_0} \quad (6)$$

$$v_{\perp} = s \frac{e^2 \mu_0 v_{-} \sin\theta}{4\pi m r_0}, \quad \text{where } s \text{ is the electron's spin parameter.} \quad (7)$$

From the electron potential energy formula $E = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r} = 2m_0c^2$, during electron-positron annihilation we have $r = r_0$

$$\text{Thus, obtain: } r_0 = \frac{e^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 m_0 c^2} \quad (8)$$

Substituting $m = \gamma m_0$, the Lorentz transformation factor $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - (\frac{v}{c})^2}}$

together with r_0 into Eq. (7), we obtain:

$$v_{\perp} = 2s \frac{v_{-} \sin\theta}{\gamma} \quad (9)$$

When v_{-} is relatively small, $\gamma = 1$, because v_{\perp} cannot be greater than v_{-} . Only when the spin parameter $s = -\frac{1}{2}$ and $\sin\theta$ takes the value -1 (indicating left-handedness)

do we have $v_{\perp} = v_{-}$. This provides a reasonable new method for determining the spin parameter. The electron's trajectory is a cylindrical helix. When the electron's speed approaches the speed of light, $v_{-} \approx c$, $\gamma \approx \infty$, $v_{\perp} = 0$; only then does the electron's trajectory tend toward a straight line. For the positron, the spin parameter is $s = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\sin\theta$ takes the value +1 (indicating right-handedness). When v_{-} is relatively small, $\gamma = 1$, and we also have $v_{\perp} = v_{-}$. When the positron's speed approaches the speed of light, $v_{-} \approx c$, $\gamma \approx \infty$, $v_{\perp} = 0$; the positron's trajectory likewise tends toward a straight line.

In bubble-chamber photographs (or nuclear emulsion photographs) taken in a magnetic field, electrons produced by gamma rays are observed to rotate to the left, while positrons rotate to the right. This experimental result confirms that assigning a spin of $-\frac{1}{2}$ to the electron and $+\frac{1}{2}$ to the positron is correct.

Electrons in atoms also move along cylindrical helical trajectories. In some atoms the electrons move in the forward direction, while in others they move in the reverse direction. In the Stern–Gerlach experiment, a silver atom has only one outer-shell electron; however, in some atoms this electron moves forward, whereas in others it moves backward. The magnetic moment of an electron depends on its direction of motion, so these atoms generate magnetic moments of opposite sign. When a beam of Ag atoms passes through a gradient magnetic field, some atoms experience an upward force and others a downward force, causing the beam to split into two lines. For the same reason, atomic beams of H, Li, Na, K, Cu, and Au also split into two lines in a gradient magnetic field.

In contrast, He, Ar, Sn, Pb, Cd, and Hg atoms have two outer-shell electrons moving in opposite directions. The magnetic moments produced by these two electrons cancel each other, so the atomic beams of these elements do not split into two lines in a gradient magnetic field. In this way, both the Stern–Gerlach experiment and the

phenomenon that an electron beam does not split into two beams in a magnetic field can be explained simultaneously.

Only when two electrons in a molecule or atom move in opposite directions can they form an electron pair; their magnetic moments then cancel each other, bringing the system to its lowest energy. According to Lenz's law, when the magnetic field produced by the outer electrons of the pair is opposite in direction to the external magnetic field, the system's energy is minimized. An electron-pair system at minimum energy is highly stable. Therefore, the formation of electron pairs in molecules or atoms is a necessary condition for the emergence of diamagnetism.

Table 1. Molar magnetic susceptibility of closed-shell atoms [11]

Atom	He	Ne	Ar	Kr	Xe
Number of outer and near outer-shell electrons	2	8	16	26	44
Theoretically predicted diamagnetism		8.08	16.16	26.26	44.44
Experimental diamagnetism	-2.02	-6.96	-19.3	-29.0	-45.5

From Table 1 it can be seen that, when a Xe atom has a total of 44 electrons in its outer and sub-outer shells, there are $44/2 = 22$ electron pairs. A simple calculation of the molar magnetic susceptibility gives

$$(44/2) \times (-2.02) = -44.44,$$

which differs from the experimental molar susceptibility value of -45.5 by about 3%. From Ne to Xe, the electron pairs formed by two electrons exhibit strong stability, and inner-shell electrons can be neglected due to shielding effects. Elements whose outer shells contain paired electrons—such as He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe, Zn, Cd, Hg, Sn, and Pb—are all diamagnetic.

There are mainly four ways in which molecules or atoms can exhibit diamagnetism:

1. Electron pairing within a single atom, where two electrons form an electron pair. Examples include He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe, Zn, Cd, Hg, Sn, Pb, and other elements.

2. Electron pairing formed by two single-electron atoms within a molecule, for example H_2 , F_2 , Cl_2 , Br_2 , I_2 and other elements.

3. Formation of compound molecules by two different kinds of atoms. For example, in Cu_2O , Cu loses one electron and O gains two electrons, so all electrons in the molecule are paired, making the molecule diamagnetic. In CuO , Cu loses two electrons, leaving one unpaired electron in the molecule, so the molecule is paramagnetic. For the same reason, the $CuCl$ molecule contains only electron pairs and is diamagnetic, whereas the $CuCl_2$ molecule contains one unpaired electron and is paramagnetic [11].

4. Formation of electron pairs by single electrons from two atoms within a solid crystal cell, as in Cu, Ag, Au, Ga, In, Tl, As, Sb, Bi, and others. For example, metallic Cu has a face-centered cubic crystal structure; within the unit cell, the magnetic moments of the atoms cancel each other, causing the crystal cell as a whole to exhibit diamagnetism. If mechanical deformation destroys the crystal structure of metallic Cu, the diamagnetism can be destroyed and paramagnetism appears; the greater the deformation, the stronger the paramagnetism. After deformation, annealing can restore the crystal structure, and diamagnetism reappears [12].

Not all atoms with paired outer-shell electrons can form stable electron pairs. For example, Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba atoms have relatively thick outer electron shells and cannot form stable electron pairs, so they exhibit paramagnetism. Al also has a relatively thick outer electron shell, cannot form stable electron pairs, and is therefore paramagnetic.

For atoms with only one outer-shell electron, such as Li, Na, K, Rb, and Cs, the crystal structure is body-centered cubic. The magnetic moment of the atom at the center of the unit cell cannot be canceled, so these materials can only exhibit paramagnetism.

At low temperatures, electron pairs are more stable and the resulting diamagnetism is stronger. If a multiply connected network of such pairs can be formed, the material can become a superconductor; in this case, the electron pairs are what are known as Cooper pairs.

Conclusion

1. Electron spin is the electron moving forward along a cylindrical helical trajectory.
2. This paper proposes a new method for determining the spin parameter.
3. Diamagnetism arises only when two electrons moving in opposite directions form an electron pair within a molecule or atom; molecules or atoms can exhibit diamagnetism through four specific mechanisms.

Author contributions

Yc.T. propose a theory; interpreted the data; and substantially revised the manuscript.

Zy.T. interpreted the data and drafted the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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